

ETYMOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH TOPONYMS

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ABSTRACT

Toponyms characterized the essential unit of that from the ancient time they have been an integral part of human life and will continue to be so. Because we know through the investigation of toponyms different peoples and nations' history, geographical places, climate, values, location and many other important features. The main purpose of this article is to study the similarities and differences between the history of Uzbek and English place names, how they were named.

Introduction

Toponyms have a special place as a scientific term because this term is comprehensive which means settlements, residential areas: republic, city, province, street, village, dacha, mahalla, guzar, district; water basins: ocean, sea, river, pool, lake, reservoir, stream; The people who own the names of each place. but the science of history deals with the task of when it was created, by whom, and why.

Each toponym has its own meaning and function as a word. Place names in different regions of our republic are the reason why their history is so named. The Mongol king built a palace for himself, and it was called the palace «Qarshi» that tower is now the name of the region since XIV century. At that time the temple was called

«buhar» in Sanskrit. It is named after the Bukhara region of Uzbekistan. Besides that Andijan means is a river bank. If we pay attention to history there are lots of such kind of suffixes "-kent, -duvon, -gan, -kon, -tim, rabot, saroy, -qand" which expressed place names. According to some researchers, "Toponyms are constituent parts of cartography and topography. It needed some centuries foretymology to develop as a scientific discipline from the early attempts of etymologies in Platons dialogue Kratylos (see www.christianlehmann.eu [Schriftenverzeichnis → Etymologie; accessed 10-01-2016]) and by the Greek Stoics until the present day. . And with the focus on place names one can add, that etymology is moreover a scientific method,

which opens an interface to the large variety of human actions in time and space, because toponyms own a special position within linguistics and exert manifold functions expressed through their lexical, structural and historical peculiarities.

Toponyms one of the interesting science for researchers which lots of scientists investigated in this field. Uzbek scientists as T.Nafasov, A.Otajonova, A.Ishaev, K.Nazarov, Z.Dusimov wrote a few books and articles in this direction. For instance, T.Nafasov is the author of "Dictionary of Uzbek toponyms" that for school and lyceum pupils. He wrote the first linguistic monograph on Uzbek toponymy in Uzbekistan. In this source is a linguistic expression of toponyms, a verbal description of the history of the people, the names of different places are clearly explained. Besides that In this work, the basics of naming, etymology, structural-grammatical structure and construction of toponyms in the territory of Kashkadarya region were studied in detail. Later, the scientist not only studied the toponyms of Kashkadarya region, but also carried out ethnolinguistic analysis of toponyms of southern Uzbekistan, published an explanatory dictionary of toponyms of Uzbekistan. The research of the well-known geographer S. Karaev also plays a special role in the historical and scientific analysis of toponyms in the territory of Uzbekistan. In this work, the historical and modern toponyms of the territory of Uzbekistan are analyzed in depth in a comparative-historical direction. The scientist's doctoral dissertation was devoted to the analysis of Uzbek oysters. In general, the most studied place names among onomastic units in Uzbekistan are toponyms, and such

research should be expanded and deepened in the future. On this basis, a solid foundation is being laid for the creation of a map of toponyms of Uzbekistan, a perfect multi-volume annotated dictionary.

As for English toponyms "The Book of English Place Names: How Our Towns and Villages Got Their Names" Kindle Edition by Caroline Taggart, "A History of English Place Names and Where They Came From" by John Moss that described the origins of the names of many English towns, hamlets, and villages date as far back as Saxon times, when kings like Alfred the Great established fortified borough towns to defend against the Danes. , "An Index to the Historical Place Names of Cornwall: Volume 2 - L to Z" by Chris Bond, "A Concise Dictionary of Cornish Place-Names" by Craig Weatherhill, Michael Everson (Editor) which Many people first take an interest in the Cornish language because they are curious to learn more about the distinctive and fascinating place names of Cornwall. The key to understanding the meaning of these place-names is language. In recent years four of Poulton-Smith's books [Coates, 2012; 2013], all dealing with counties that onomastic literature. A typical entry for a single name with a complicated history is given below: the entry for the city of Bristol from the third volume of *The Place-Names of Gloucestershire* by A. H. Smith, which constitutes volume 40 of the Survey (published in 1964) [PN Gloucs, 3, 83–84]

While we are learning toponymic system through the comparing Uzbek and English toponyms, we pay attention to their etymological peculiarities. For example, the emergence of many Uzbek toponyms depend on natural geographical conditions

(relief), ethnic composition of the population, occupations and occupations of people, excavations. riches, historical figures and events. However language changes are the main sources of English toponyms. Place-names may also be compounds composed of elements derived from two or more languages from different periods. The majority of the toponyms predate the radical changes in the English language triggered by the Norman Conquest, and some Celtic names even predate the arrival of the Anglo-Saxons in the first millennium AD.

Discussion

While we are learning etymological peculiarities of Uzbek and English toponyms through the scientists investigation, we refer to the books of T. Nafasov "Dictionary of Uzbek toponyms". And "The Book of English Place Names: How Our Towns and Villages Got Their Names" Kindle Edition by Caroline Taggart is one of the best example for reveal toponymic classification and its system. Through the comparing these 2 books, I came across lots of data, tried to catch similarities and differences Uzbek and English toponyms. For example, T. Nafasov His "Explanatory Dictionary of Toponyms of Uzbekistan" (1988) mainly describes the etymology of microtoponyms in southern Uzbekistan. However, the etymological explanation of some historical toponyms in the region, such as Boysun, Kesh, Chaganyon, Qarsihi, are also given. This book describes the importance of toponyms, the structure of the dictionary, and the place names of many places in alphabetical order, their meaning, the history of their origin. For example, 'ALAMLI' is the name of *G'allaorol district which means the tomb of the saints, or the*

place of the martyr's grave, is a rag-spot on a tree branch or a stick, as is the village near the cemetery;

'ARABSAROY' the name of Karmana district, which means the palace of Arabs;

'ASAKA' –one of the city of Andijan which was the city of the Saks, renaming assakana.

Every place names origin and etymology are interesting, exotic and unusual.

However the book "The Book of English Place Names: How Our Towns and Villages Got Their Names" Kindle Edition by Caroline Taggart is organized by region, making this use a bit more convenient than a purely alphabetical arrangement. Besides that lots of places and data was written in a intelligent and funny way. But such books would be interesting and understandable to the reader when enriched with pictures.

After reading these two books, I came to the conclusion that as a young linguist, this topic is very relevant and will greatly contribute to the enrichment of our vocabulary.

Also discussion part include the a few principles of toponyms:

a) According to localization. The term "our" toponyms implies geographical names, denoting objects within the examined language area ("our" names of Great Britain and the USA are Washington, Alabama, New York, Mississippi, Birmingham, Thames, London, etc.). "Their" toponyms represent geographical names, denoting objects outside the language area in question (Norway, Argentina, Qatar, Sierra Leone, The Netherlands, Thailand, Spain).

b) According to the degree of place names are *primary* and *non-primary*.

Primary toponyms: Australia, Boston, Lake Superior, Uychi district, Yorkatay NCM, Shaykxontoxur which are derived from common names. The Lake Aydar, Amir Temur st., Hercules, Washington are the examples of non-primary toponyms are derived from proper names.

c) Next principle based on chronological classification that *archaic and current* place names. *Yaksart and Jayhun* are the archaic ones, however *Sirdarya and Amudarya* are contemporary place names.

d) According to the structure toponyms are divided to *simple, derivative, compound and complex*.

Simple – *Tashkent, Russia, Chirchiq, London, Chine, Amazon, Niagara, Africa and so on.*

Derivative – *Yunusobod, Birmingham, Uzbekistan, California;*

Compound – *Surxandarya, Oceanside, Newtown, Bartonblonte, Darlington, Bristol;*

Complex – *South America, Central Asia, Arctic Ocean, Sobir Rahimov st., Northone Brun, Qora-tepa (blackhill), Oqqo'rg'on (whitebarrow).*

Conclusion

In general, a toponym is a collection of place names in a specific area. The name of any science, what it means, where the name first appeared, is geographical on the one hand, and toponymy on the other. Toponymy, the science of geographical names, is closely related to the sciences of geology, geomorphology, and biogeography, which study the structure and properties of a specific region of the planet. This research paper revealed a few etymological peculiarities of Uzbek and English toponyms through the scientists' work.

Everything in the world has a name. People move from one place to another, from one street next to another, to the hills, to the towns and villages invented names to distinguish them from each other.

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